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TECHNOLOGY**

**AN IMPROVED LUNG CANCER SEGMENTATION AND DETECTION MODEL
FROM CT-SCAN IMAGES USING DEEP LEARNING**

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ABSTRACT

The most promising strategy to improve a patient's chances of survival is to discover cancer early. This research uses an artificial neural network to construct a computer-aided classification approach for computed tomography (CT) images of the lungs. From the CT scan images, the complete lung is segmented, and the parameters are determined from the segmented image. Lung cancer is one of the most lethal cancers that results in a large number of deaths worldwide. The only method to increase a patient's chances of survival is to discover lung cancer early. A computed tomography (CT) scan is used to locate a tumor and determine the extent of malignancy throughout the body. In this research, we develop a model for Segmentation and Detection of Lung Cancer that is known as a SDLC System using K-means with Swarm-based Grasshopper Optimization (SGO) algorithm for CT-scan images using Deep Learning is proposed. For the autonomous lung cancer diagnosis in CT images, a novel approach is offered. The concept of Maximally Stable Extremal Regions (MSER) along with the SGO algorithm is used for feature selection. The concept of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is utilized to train the SDLC system on the basis of selected feature from MSER feature set via fitness function. The Optimized CNN is used to train the SDLC model using a modified K-means based Lung nodule segmentation. The accuracy of lung region segmentation is improved by employing the K-means along with the SGO algorithm. As a result, the SDLC model's classification performance has improved in comparison to previous studies in terms of precision rate and the achieved precision is near to 94.5%.

Keywords: Segmentation and Detection of Lung Cancer (SDLC) System, MSER descriptor, K-means, Swarm-based Grasshopper Optimization (SGO), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and CNN.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer is most common type of malignant cancer in the world. Basically, it is a disease that happens because of uncontrolled cell growth in the human lung tissues. This growth might lead to metastasis, known as the adjacent tissue invasion and infiltration ahead of the lungs [1]. The prognosis and treatment are dependent on the histological cancer type, the degree of spread (the stage), and the status of the patient's performance. The possible treatments comprise chemotherapy, surgery, and radiotherapy [2]. Survival of the patient depends on overall health, onstage, and another factor, but on all only 14% of people diagnosed with lung cancer and survive five years after the diagnosis [3]. The symptoms of human lung cancer detection include:

- ☞ Hemoptysis (coughing up blood),
- ☞ Dyspnea (shortness of breath with activity),
- ☞ Regular coughing pattern changes,
- ☞ Pain in Chest,
- ☞ Dysphonia (hoarse voice),
- ☞ Heavy weight loss, fatigue, and loss of appetite,

Human lung cancers also known as 'Bronchogenic Carcinomas', and it is divided into ensuing two types:

- ❖ SCLC (Small cell lung cancers)
- ❖ NSCLC (Non-small cell lung cancers)

Fig. 1. Human Lung Cancer Types

The classification is dependent on tumor cell microscopic appearance in scanned image. Therefore, the distinction among both is important [4]. Where, SCLC consists of around 20% of lung cancers and is known as most aggressive with rapidly growing as compared to other lung cancer types. SCLC (is strongly linked to cigarette smoking, having 1% of these tumors in non-smokers. SCLC (metastasizes quickly for numerous sites in the body and is mainly frequently discovered after they have spread expansively. The specific cell appearances saw when the examinations of SCLC samples under the microscope take place and are known as oat cell carcinomas. NSCLC are the main common lung cancers, with about 80% of all lung cancers [6]. So in this research work, we focused to develop a Segmentation and Detection of Lung Cancer (SDLC) System from CT-Scan images using Deep Learning. The concept of the K-means with Swarm-based Grasshopper Optimization (SGO) technique is used to improve the lung nodules segmentation accuracy and then the concept of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is used as classifier to train the SDLC system by using dataset of CT-scan images and the major contributions are highlighted as:

- We presents a brief survey about the existing lung nodule segmentation and detection techniques for CT-scan images to find out the inferences drawn.
- We developed a K-means method based improved segmentation algorithm for lung nodule using SGO technique with a novel fitness function.
- To extract feature from segmented Region of Lung (ROL), MSER descriptor is used with SGO as a feature selection approach.
- To detect and classify the lung cancer from CT-scan images, the concept of CNN is used as an Artificial Intelligence (AI) technique.
- At the last, we make a comparison with existing works to validate the SDLC model, based on the Precision, Recall, F-measure, Execution Time, Accuracy and Error Rate.

The research article is organized as follows. Section II cover a brief survey about related work and materials and methodological parts of this work are discussed in section III. The simulation results of proposed SDLC system are shown and discussed in section IV and the conclusions are drawn in section V.

2. RELATED WORK

There are many methods already used to address the diagnosis and diagnosis of lung cancer by focusing on the issues of stage failure but in this section of the study article, we focus on identifying the problem with the SDLC program. In 2019, W. Chen et al. did research on the Hybrid Segmentation Network (HSN) for the SCLC Segmentation and used a CT database (Compiled at Shandong Cancer Hospital Linked to Shandong University). This model combines lightweight CNN to learn 3D distance information with 2D CNN which can read fine semantic information in images, which is an important step in obtaining better cancer classification results. They achieved a high system performance based on the average Dice average of 0.888, the average sensitivity rate of 0.872 and an average accuracy of 0.909. The number of images is small in the database and the overall accuracy is close to 88%. You need to improve through use and method development method [7]. That same year, K. Senthil Kumar et al. we have analyzed the performance of five development algorithms, namely, k-means integration, k-median integration, particle efficiency, moderate particle development, and guaranteed optimization of convergence swarm optimization (GCP SO) particles, to remove the tumor in the picture of the lungs has been developed and analyzed. The performance of the central, flexible and intermediate filters in the pre-screening phase was compared, and it was proven that a compatible adapter filter is more suitable for

medical CT imaging. In addition, image brightness was enhanced using adaptive histogram equalization. Improved image quality with advanced quality is less than four algorithms. Visual results were confirmed in 20 pulmonary image samples using MATLAB, and it was noted that GCP SO had a high accuracy of 95.89% [8]. In 2018, Arulmurugan *et al.* introduced a wavelet feature based feature extraction with a neural network as a classification algorithm. The proposed separator produced 92.6% accuracy. The training was performed using 70% photography and 30% photographic testing taken from complete photographs [9]. Singh *et al.* in 2018 showed an effective way to obtain and classify CT scan images related to lung cancer into a dangerous and dangerous category. In this program, images are first processed using image processing techniques, and then the classified reading algorithms are classified. The texture elements were extracted along with the mathematical features and provided a variety of features extracted from the class dividers. Seven different categories known as the closest k separator k, the supporting vector machine divider, decision tree section, multinomial naive classifier of Bayes, stochastic gradient descent classifier, random class classifier, and class multi-layer perceptron (MLP) was used. From the survey, it was found that the accuracy of the MLP separator is 88.55% higher compared to other dividers [10]. Pol Cirujeda *et al.* in 2016 he used a texture blending function that maintains a variety of spatial interactions between features. This represents an important solution to overcoming the reversal of old integration tasks for example scale, in which the interaction between local responses of pairs of tailor operators is mixed between different parts of manure. In the first step, strategies are used to predict duplication of NSCLC modules from pre-treatment CT scans. In the second step, the proposed methods were used to calculate the type of duplicate of the NSCLC nodes based on the standard multiplication separator. This recognition opens up new research guidelines on how to use morphological tissue structures to detect cancer attacks and requires further confirmation and investigation. The author focuses on the captivity of nodular tissue, and combines it with other factors such as tumor shape, size, and modeling orthogonal information [11]. M. Kurkure and A. Thakare in 2016 focused on the development and design of a system for early diagnosis and diagnosis of lung cancer in CT, PET and X-ray imaging. To improve the results, a genetic algorithm is used that allows diagnoses to detect lumps in the lungs in the early stages of lung cancer. In order to classify the various categories of cancer images accurately and quickly, the use of Naïve Bayes and the genetic algorithm was designed to overcome the difficulty of producing excellent features with 80% accuracy [12]. C. Divya and J. Varun in 2016 proposed machine learning methods to diagnose lung cancer. Automatic diagnostics used in machine learning often depend on factors taken from the classification of individual objects, which can be difficult to perform automatically. The author works by predicting and preventing various medical diseases using PCA; canny edge detection techniques have been used using pre-processing and background processing has been used. First the edge detection is performed and then the removal of the feature is done to determine the fixed number of the feature to distinguish between infected and non-infectious diseases. Comparisons with the SURF method were performed and it was found that the PCA method was better than the SURF method [13]. Hala M *et al.* in 2016 the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm (ABC) and Vector Support Machine (SVM) were proposed to measure the accuracy of selected genes. The data set consists of two classes of six binary and multiclass microarrays. Also comparisons between pre-existing strategies such as ABC, GA, and PSO and ABC-SVM are provided. It has been concluded that the proposed SVM-ABC algorithm performs better than SVM-PSO, SVM-GA strategies [14].

So, in this research, we try to solve the existing problem by utilizing the concept of MSER as feature descriptor along with SGO with CNN to train and classify the lung cancer from CT-scan images.

3. METHODS & MATERIALS

In this research article, we proposed a SDLC system using the concept of hybridization of K-means with SGO algorithm for ROL segmentation from CT-scan images and then extract MSER features from segmented ROL. The details about implementation phase of the proposed DSLC system are given in the below section of this article and the architecture of proposed SDLC system is shown in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Architecture of SDLC System

The procedural and working steps of proposed SDLC system is described below:

Step 1: To design a model using the concept of GUI for simulation of proposed system in order to classify the lung cancer from the CT-scan images.

Step 2: Upload CT-scan images for the training as well classification of proposed system.

Step 3: Apply pre-processing on the uploaded CT-scan images to segment the ROL of lung using the K-means clustering technique with SGO. Pre-Processing is done to remove various type of noise that are inherited in the CT-scan images to enhance the quality of image in proposed SDLC system,

Step 4: Develop a code for the objective function of the SGO for minimization of irrelevant area from the segmented ROL of CT-scan images using the morphological operations. Algorithm of ROL segmentation is written as:

Algorithm 1: ROL Segmentation
Input: Image → Input CT-scan Image
Output: SegImg → Segmented Image
Apply K-means Initialize an estimated group (G) Calculate size of Image in terms of [Row, Col.] Define initial Bimg and Fimg with random Centroid $C = C1$ and $C2$ While Itr = maximum For i → 1 to all Row For j → 1 to all column If Image (i,j) == C1 Bimg (1) = Image (i,j) Else if Image (i,j) == C2 Fimg (2) = Image (i,j) End – If Adjust Centroid C using their mean $C = \text{Average}(\text{Bimg}, \text{Fimg})$ and repeat End – For End – For End – While From Fimg image extract the ROI SegImg = SGO [ROL] Marking with different colors on SegImg Return: SegImg as a ROL End – Function

Based on the develop algorithm with the objective function for SGO algorithm for minimization of irrelevant area from the segmented ROL using the CT-scan images with the morphological operations. Algorithm 1 depicts the proposed ROL segmentation framework that helps to train the SDLC model with semantic information into a single model. To deal with the anisotropic dimensions of CT-scan images volumes and lower the computational cost of the CNN, pattern net-based CNN is used. ROL segmentation algorithm helps to find out the most relevant feature and the sample of the segmented image using the proposed ROL segmentation algorithm is show in the Fig. 3.

Fig. 3.ROL Segmentation Sample

Step 5: After that develop a code for feature extraction from the segmented ROL of CT-scan images using the MSER descriptor technique. Algorithm of MSER is written as:

Algorithm 2: MSER Descriptor
Input: SegImg → Segmented ROL
Output: MSER-Points → MSER feature set of ROL
Calculate size of SegImg, [R, C] = size (SegImg)
For I = 1 → R
For J = 1 → C
Scaled Image = SegImg (I, J, 8) // Scaling of SegImg into 8 X 8
Extrema Point = Max Extrema (Scaled Image (I, J))
Key-point = Localization (Extrema Point (I, J))
Checking of variation in Key-points
If Variation occurs
Discard those key points
Else
MSER-Points = Key-point (I, J)
End – If
End – For
End – For
Return: MSER-Points as a MSER feature set of ROL
End – Function

Step 6: For the relevant feature selection from the extracted MSER feature sets, SGO will be used as a feature selection or optimization algorithm along with the novel fitness function. Feature selection algorithm is written as:

Algorithm 3: SGO-based Feature Selection
Input: MSER-Points → MSER feature set of image
Output: OMSE-Points → Optimized MSER feature set of image

```

Initialize the SGO with their operating functions
- Population Size
- Define fitness function of SGO
- Fit_function_PSO = True;      if  $f_s > f_t$ 
                          False; otherwise
Calculate size of MSER-Points (R, C)
For I = 1 → R
For J = 1 → C
Fs = MSER-Points (I, J)
Ft = Threshold (I, J) = Average (MSER-Points)
Fit_function_SGO = Call Fit_function_PSO (Fs, Ft)
OMSER-Points = SGO (Fit_function_SGO, SGO functions)
End – For
End – For
Returns: OMSER-Points
End – Function

```

Step 7: Initialize the CNN for classification purpose using two phases, namely, training and testing with CNN as classifier. After the training of system, save the trained structure which is used in the classification section to classify the lung cancer from the CT-scan images and the algorithm of SDLC-CNN is written as:

Algorithm 4: SDLC-CNN

Input: OMSER-Points and T → Optimized MSER feature of image as training data and their types as a target or category

Output: SDLC-Net-Structure → Trained structure with Classified Results

```

Initialize the Pattern net based ANN:
- Number of Epochs (E) // Iterations used by CNN
- Number of Neurons (N) // Used as a carrier
- Performance: Cross entropy, Gradient, Error Histogram and Validation
- Data Division: Random
For i = 1 → OMSER-Points
If OMSER-Point belongs to Type 1
Group (1) = Feature from the 1st Categories
Else if OMSER-Point belongs to Type 2
Group (2) = Feature from the 2nd Categories
Else
Group (3) = Feature from the 3rd Categories
End – If
End – For
Initialized the pattern net
Pattern-Net-Structure = Patternnet (N)
Set the training parameters according to the requirements and train the system
SDLC-Net-Structure = Train (Pattern-Net-Structure, OMSER-Points, Group)
Test Data Group = Sim (SDLC-Net-Structure, Current Image)
If Test Data Group = 1
Classified Results = Abnormal
Else if Test Data Group = 2
Classified Results = Normal
Else if Test Data Group = 3
Classified Results = Sorry
End – If
Return: Pattern-Net-Structure as a trained structure with Classified Results
End – Function

```

Step 8: In the testing phase, the test CT-scan image is uploaded and repeats the steps from 3 to 6. In the classification section, test CT-scan image feature is matched with trained CNN structure and return result type.

Step 9: At last of simulation, the performance parameters of propose system will be calculated in terms of Precision, Recall, F-Measure, Error Rate, Accuracy and Execution Time.

The simulation results analysis of the proposed SDLC system is discussed in the next section of this research article with the comparison to validate the system efficiency.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Description of the simulation results are analyzed in this section of research article for the proposed SDLC system to segment and classify the lung nodules from the CT-scan images.

CT-Scan Image Dataset: We use VIA/I-ELCAP Public Access Research Database. The Sample dataset of CT-scan images is shown in the Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Sample of Dataset CT-scan Images

After following the above defined steps, at the end, performance has been analyzed in terms of different parameters as discussed in result and discussion section. So, the proposed SDLC system is test on the CT-scan image dataset of lungs. The simulation results of the proposed SDLC system using the CNN is given in the Table I and their graphical representation is also described in the below section of the research article.

TABLE I. SIMULATION RESULTS ANALYSIS OF SDLC SYSTEM

Sample Size	Precision	Recall	F-measure	Accuracy (%)	Error (%)
← CNN →					
10	0.840393	0.819602	0.829867299	83.336	16.664
20	0.857545	0.830016	0.843555961	83.6331	16.3669
50	0.869818	0.837296	0.853247214	84.2265	15.7735
100	0.872317	0.841588	0.856677026	84.6732	15.3268
200	0.881986	0.844426	0.86279742	86.1182	13.8818
500	0.882166	0.859023	0.870440697	86.3871	13.6129
1000	0.889287	0.863351	0.876127096	87.1653	12.8493
Average	0.870502	0.870502	0.870502	0.870502	0.870502
← K-means with CNN →					
10	0.875617	0.861016	0.868255	88.7472	11.2528
20	0.889589	0.863454	0.876327	88.8045	11.1955
50	0.893009	0.866298	0.879451	89.4563	10.5437
100	0.894379	0.867262	0.880612	90.4168	9.5832
200	0.913313	0.86779	0.88997	90.5786	9.4214
500	0.918155	0.869156	0.892984	90.628	9.372
1000	0.918255	0.870544	0.893763	91.4267	8.5733
Average	0.900331	0.866502857	0.883051714	90.0083	9.9917
← K-means with MSER & CNN →					
10	0.901485	0.895277	0.89837	90.9179	9.0821
20	0.908611	0.903741	0.906169	91.0614	8.9386
50	0.91083	0.90745	0.909137	91.8893	8.1107
100	0.915879	0.910929	0.913397	93.2392	6.7608
200	0.919705	0.914236	0.916962	94.1993	5.8007
500	0.936661	0.918896	0.927693	94.6291	5.3709
1000	0.94915	0.925637	0.937246	94.8896	5.1104

Average	0.920331571	0.910880857	0.915567714	92.97511429	7.024885714
← K-means + SGO with CNN →					
10	0.93082	0.924715	0.927757	94.0269	5.9731
20	0.937211	0.933087	0.935144	94.5022	5.4978
50	0.938125	0.938099	0.938112	94.6946	5.3054
100	0.944067	0.938551	0.941301	95.6956	4.3044
200	0.949664	0.939535	0.944572	95.7037	4.2963
500	0.95368	0.94242	0.948017	96.1357	3.8643
1000	0.959075	0.949965	0.954498	96.1449	3.8551
Average	0.944663143	0.938053143	0.941343	95.27194286	4.728057143
← K-means + SGO with MSER & CNN →					
10	0.921594	0.920854	0.921224	96.0547	3.9453
20	0.922882	0.929214	0.926037	96.3373	3.6627
50	0.947636	0.937729	0.942656	96.62	3.38
100	0.948087	0.943189	0.945632	96.7182	3.2818
200	0.953313	0.945264	0.949271	97.4257	2.5743
500	0.960105	0.965301	0.962696	97.7079	2.2921
1000	0.97657	0.968168	0.972351	97.821	2.179
Average	0.94717	0.944246	0.945695	96.95497	3.045029

Fig. 5. Simulation results of SDLC system (a) Precision (b) Recall (c) F-measure

From the Table I and Fig. 5, we observed that the simulation results of proposed SDLC system using the concept of hybridization of the K-means with SGO and CNN with MSER is superior to others modules in terms of the performance parameters, but to validate the efficiency of system, we need to compare with existing work based on their precision in Table II.

TABLE II. COMPARISON WITH EXISTING WORKS

Parameters	W. Chen et al. (2019)	Proposed SDLC System
Precision Rate	90.9	94.5

Above Table II demonstrated the comparative analysis of proposed SDLC work with exiting work presented W. Chen et al. (2019) in term of precision that is 94.5% correspondingly.

Fig. 6. Comparison of Proposed with Existing Work using Precision

Based on the comparative analysis with existing work by W. Chen et al. (2019), the proposed SDLC system achieved better precision by utilizing the concept of hybridization K-means along with SGO algorithm and MSER for ROL segmentation from CT-scan.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, an improved lung cancer segmentation and detection (SDLC) model from CT-scan images using Deep Learning is proposed. For sustainable operations, an evaluation-based test algorithm known as SGO algorithm along with K-means is employed to enhance the segmentation accuracy of CT-scan data in terms of the testing process. The Convolution Neural Network-based configuration method was used to eliminate irrelevant features from CT scans that is extracted using MSER descriptor. The insertion layer, the consolidation layer, and the convolution layer are the three layers that make up this system. Previously, a variety of CT imaging services were provided to assess the efficacy of this work using a few characteristics such as Error (percent), Classification Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F-measure are calculated. The observed result of proposed SDLC work in terms of precision is more than 94% by using the concept of K-means clustering with SGO for improvement in segmentation technique and by using the CNN as classifier. The proposed model used the lung ROI segmentation from the CT-scan images with the help of hybridization of K-means along with SGO for the accurate diagnosis of lung cancer in early stage. However, in the diagnosis and classification of lung cancer, various extensions still to be undertaken; these include optimization of the segmented region of lung form CT-scan image. The proposed system can be extended with hybrid feature optimization technique with natural computing approaches after feature extraction process for the detection of lung cancer with maximum accuracy in future.

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